

The Role of Students in the Telangana Movement –A Study of Hyderabad District

C. Yadagiri

Research Scholar, Department of Political Science
Osmania Univesity
Hyderabad

Abstract:

The important significance of the student movement in the Separate Telangana campaign is evident. The individuals had a significant role in elevating the prominence of the demand for the establishment of Telangana State, particularly through intellectual engagements such as dialogues, workshops, seminars, and public gatherings organized by esteemed academic institutions like Kakatiya and Osmania universities. Several student organizations, namely TRSV, ABVP, NSUI, PDSU, AISF, and Dalith Student Organization, collectively demonstrated their solidarity with the Telangana agitation. The students showcased their solidarity by establishing a student Joint Action Committee (JAC) at Kakatiya University on November 17, 2009. They expressed their endorsement of KCR, the leader of TRS, who was undertaking a hunger strike in pursuit of a particular objective.

The active engagement of students can be ascribed to their enduring consciousness of the Telangana cause, which has been deeply instilled in them since their early years. Their profound comprehension and unwavering dedication rendered them the fundamental support system of the revolution. This article discusses the significance of the student movements that became instruments in the formation of Telangana State.

Keywords: Telangana campaign, student organizations, unwavering dedication, student movements, separate state etc.

Introduction

The student movement that emerged during the Separate Telangana movement in Telangana was undoubtedly a very influential and impactful social movement in the region—approximately twelve years after the establishment of Andhra Pradesh, the populace of Telangana commenced articulating their discontentment with the governing authorities, asserting their desire for the fulfilment of the pledged assurances. The origins of this struggle

can be traced back to the formative years of post-colonial India. The first indications became apparent through the non-Mulki agitation in 1952, which was succeeded by what might be regarded as the third wave manifested in the second non-Mulki agitation in 1956, and the year 1969 witnessed a notable escalation in the persistent pursuit of establishing an independent state of Telangana, also called the agitation. The sequence above of agitations serves as a testament to the enduring and ingrained aspiration of the Telangana populace to establish a separate state.

Notably, the movement's inception can be traced back to December 6, 1968, when a group of students from Vivek Vardhini College in Hyderabad initiated a parade. Regrettably, the procession encountered instances of violent aggression from individuals enlisted by proponents of integration, as well as from law enforcement personnel. In light of these occurrences, protests were orchestrated in Khammam and Warangal. The momentum of the campaign experienced a sustained increase, disseminating to several regions inside Telangana, encompassing Nizamabad. This historical time holds great significance in the annals of Telangana's history and is commonly known as the "Black Day," symbolizing the arduous trials and tribulations encountered throughout the movement.

On January 8, 1969, an individual named Ravindranath commenced an indefinite hunger strike in the Khammam region, aiming to advocate for the safeguarding of Telangana. The precise underlying factors driving his activities remain ambiguous. However, this was initially a protest confined to a certain geographical area. Nevertheless, as the strike persisted, it acquired more support and momentum. On the fifth day of the hunger strike, students in Khammam resorted to increasingly extreme measures, including the vandalization of government offices and the deliberate ignition of road transportation corporation (RTC) buses. The action above resulted in the intensification of the crisis and garnered increased focus on the underlying issue.

In a display of solidarity with their counterparts in Khammam, students in Warangal also orchestrated protests, augmenting the movement's scope and influence. This occurrence exemplifies how seemingly minor actions may ignite substantial social and political movements.

The emergency meeting held on January 12, 1969, by the Osmania University Student Union was to evaluate the current protests occurring in several regions. During the discussion, the

union conveyed profound discontentment with the political leadership in the region. The individuals in question demonstrated a courageous act by formally requesting the resignation of Members of the Legislative Assembly (MLAs) and nine cabinet ministers from Telangana. Demonstrating unwavering determination, the students proclaimed that unless the government acceded to these stipulations, they would commence an indeterminate cessation of activities on January 15, 1969. The issuance of this request signified a notable intensification in their position. This development also underscores the progression of student demands, which have expanded in terms of both quantity and breadth as compared to the first requests presented by the all-party Telangana leaders. The statement highlights the growing intensity and resolve exhibited by the students in their endeavour to establish an independent state for Telangana.

On January 15, 1969, as per their prior declaration, students in the twin towns of Hyderabad and Secunderabad abstained from attending their academic sessions. A meeting was convened at the Nizam College grounds, where individuals assembled. It became apparent that the student body might be divided into two distinct factions: one arguing for implementing safeguards for Telangana, and the other supporting the creation of an independent state of Telangana under the guidance of Mallikarjun. The Student Union persisted with their protest and expanded the scope of their academic boycott. He issued a directive to gather all students at Nizam College on the following day at 11 a.m. During the deliberations, it became evident that the faction advocating for establishing a distinct Telangana state held a dominant position regarding popular backing.

After the conference's conclusion, Mallikarjun, the President of the Osmania University Students Association, led a student rally from the Nizam College grounds to the Abids Circle. Despite the substantial police deployment, there were sporadic occurrences of students engaging in the act of hurling stones at municipal buses. Regrettably, these events resulted in the unfortunate loss of two lives. Two individuals, Sriram Chandra and Dasthagir, aged twenty-five and ten, respectively, lost their lives as a result of police gunfire during their attempt to interrupt a felicitation ceremony honouring the Home Minister Jalagam Vengal Rao in his town of Khammam. Furthermore, in a separate occurrence at Secunderabad, an individual named Ravinder, aged eighteen, tragically perished due to the escalating turmoil inside the satyagraha movement. The instances above underscore the heightened intensity and profound seriousness of the circumstances that characterized the Telangana Movement of 1969.

Mallikarjun, the leader of the Osmania University Student Union, made a notable declaration, asserting that their protest would last until establishing an independent Telangana state. The declaration above emphasized the student movement's unwavering determination and resolute nature. It is noteworthy to acknowledge that throughout that period, there existed murmurs and conjectures regarding the potential involvement of specific politicians in orchestrating and exerting influence over the actions undertaken by student union officials, however discreetly. This observation implies the presence of political manoeuvring and strategic planning within the context of the movement. In light of the intensifying circumstances, Chief Minister Sri. Brahmananda Reddy, confronted with an expanding array of requests and persistent acts of aggression, implemented a resolute measure. The closure of all educational institutions until January 27, 1969, was officially announced. The purpose of this action was presumably to alleviate tensions and offer temporary relief from the intensifying protests and rallies.

After a ruling by the High Court, students in Khammam district commenced a protest to advocate for enforcing a 2:1 ratio in all public services, encompassing autonomous entities such as the State Electricity Board. Furthermore, they advocated for prolonging the timeframe for implementing protective measures. The political leaders of the Telangana region have shown a lack of responsiveness towards the concerns stated by student leaders despite their sincere endeavours to address the difficulties above. The absence of timely and effective communication likely contributed to the increasing dissatisfaction among the student body.

Following this, a General Body meeting of the Osmania University Students Union occurred on January 12, commencing at 10 a.m. at Nizam College. Several distinguished student leaders were invited to participate in deliberations around the Telangana safeguards. During this discussion, two divergent perspectives became apparent: one faction calling for the establishment of an independent Telangana state and another advocating for the preservation of an integrated Andhra Pradesh, accompanied by the execution of robust protective measures for the inhabitants of Telangana. The split was observed among the students, wherein certain individuals advocated for establishing an independent state. In contrast, others advocated for the integration of Andhra Pradesh with comprehensive protective measures, constituting a significant juncture in the campaign. The statement above elucidated the intricate nature and wide-ranging perspectives of the Telangana Movement.

The collective arguing for the proficient implementation of protective measures was popularly known as "safeguards," whilst individuals firmly dedicated to establishing an independent Telangana state were labelled as "separatists." To streamline and coordinate their endeavours, the safeguardists decided to function inside the framework of the Osmania University Student Organization. Conversely, the separatists established an independent entity known as Telangana Students.

The divergence in approach and strategy ultimately resulted in the forming of an Action Committee that garnered significant support inside the Telangana region. Both factions commenced arranging gatherings autonomously and instigated public displays of protest starting from January 15, 1969 onwards. Regrettably, the divide above and divergent methodologies culminated in a confrontation between the two antagonistic factions on January 18, 1969. The occurrence above highlights the profound emotional intensity and intricate diversity of perspectives in the Telangana Movement.

The Second Phase of Telangana Movement Between 1990-2009

In 1991, two notable organizations, namely the Telangana Student Front and the Telangana Liberation Student Organization, were founded within the premises of Osmania University. These groups were instrumental in advocating for the cause of Telangana. The establishment of the Kakatiya Unit of the Telangana Students Front in 1992 strengthened the presence and impact of the movement within the university.

In August 1993, Osmania University organized a significant event in the form of a national symposium on small states. The conference was started by Surendra Mohan, followed by an address presented by Justice Madav Reddy to the delegates. The seminar served as a forum for delegates from different regions of the nation to convene and partake in deliberations about the notion of tiny states, encompassing debates on the ambitions of Telangana for autonomous statehood.

The Forum for Freedom of Expression, including journalists and writers, exerted considerable influence in championing the Telangana cause throughout 1996. The individual responsible for the article's composition can be identified as a co-founder of the forum, suggesting the active participation of diverse societal factions within the movement. The resurrection of the movement was exemplified by a significant event that occurred in Warangal on November 1,

1996, at the Telangana Praja Samiti conference. The gathering garnered participation from many delegates, exceeding five thousand, representing various regions within Telangana, thereby underscoring the extensive backing for the cause above.

Subsequently, a notable convention took place in Hyderabad on December 1, 1996. Subsequently, a sequence of conferences, group assemblies, and public congregations took place in diverse locations throughout Telangana, encompassing Godavari Khani, Karimnagar, Siddipet, Jangabn, Aler, Ghanapur, Nizamabad, Khammam, Nalgonda, the historic city of Hyderabad, and Bhongir. The Bhongir meeting, specifically, demonstrated a pivotal moment. Gaddar, a highly acclaimed balladeer known for his revolutionary contributions, was the distinguished guest of honour. He appealed to the populace to initiate a wholly nonviolent campaign to attain the objective of establishing an autonomous territory. This assertion by a prominent figure further strengthened and unified the movement.

The demand for the formation of the state of Telangana continued to exist even with the quelling of the 1969 movement. The persistent desire for separate statehood in Telangana was motivated by a perceived sense of unfairness, injustice, and humiliation felt by the local population and personnel hailing from the region. The grievances arose due to various factors, including the Gentlemen's Agreement, breaches of the six-point formula, allocation of budgetary reserves, and the exploitation of irrigation water from the Godavari and Krishna rivers. In light of these persistent concerns, several institutions and platforms emerged during the latter half of the 20th century to spearhead the campaign for establishing Telangana as a separate state. The organizations that were involved in the movement for the formation of Telangana were Telangana Mahasabha, Telangana Janasabha, Telangana Students Organizations, Telangana Teachers Forum, Telangana Intellectuals Forum, Telangana Information Centre, and Telangana Study Forum. These groups endeavoured to tackle many challenges and promote the establishment of Telangana as an independent state.

The demand for a distinct Telangana region experienced a resurgence during the 1980s and 1990s, notably during the governance of the Telugu Desam Party. The Telangana Rashtra Samithi (TRS) formation in 2001 emerged as a notable achievement in the pursuit of Telangana statehood.

From the mid-2000s onwards, numerous organizations emerged to advance the pursuit of statehood for Telangana. Notable organizations that emerged during this period include the Telangana Vidyavanthula Vedika (2006), Telangana Ikya Karyacharana Committee (2006), and Telangana Dhoom Dham (2007), with several other cultural organizations. These organizations were instrumental in galvanizing and mobilizing the popular campaign for Telangana, irrespective of political alignments or party loyalties. A significant occurrence during this period was the establishment of the political Joint Action Committee in 2010. This committee convened many political bodies, including TRS, BJP, CPI(ML), and other groups. The retraction of the declaration regarding the formation process of Telangana by P. Chidambaram, the Union Home Minister, prompted the organization's founding. The occurrence above highlighted the unwavering commitment and cohesive collaboration exhibited by diverse factions in their endeavour to establish Telangana as a separate state.

The demand for establishing an independent Telangana state has been motivated by two key factors: the aspiration for the region's socio-economic progress and the preservation of its inhabitants' dignity. Notwithstanding a multitude of obstacles, encompassing elusive commitments, repressive tactics, and Machiavellian machinations, the movement has persistently garnered traction. The pressure above has been applied to both the Central and State Governments. The influence of the political environment has also been a significant factor in shaping the course of the movement. The demand for a separate state in Telangana has been consistently advocated by its residents. At the same time, political parties have frequently used this matter for electoral advantages in national and local elections. Nevertheless, after the attainment of electoral triumph, governing parties have occasionally modified their position, resulting in disenchantment among the general public.

The desire to establish Telangana State has had intermittent phases of renewal. Following a period of being marginalized until 1995, the revival of the cause was initiated through intellectual-led talks, workshops, seminars, and public gatherings held at esteemed universities such as Kakatiya University and Osmania University. The state Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) also incorporated the issue of state formation into its electoral program in 1999. Notably, in 2000, many new states, namely Chhattisgarh, Uttarakhand, and Jharkhand, were established. The Telangana State formation problem experienced a notable surge in June 2001, coinciding with the establishment of the Telangana Rashtra Samithi (TRS), a newly formed political

organization under the leadership of Mr K. Chandrasekhar Rao. The resignation of Rao from his MLA seat within the Telugu Desam Party (TDP) constituted a significant milestone in the trajectory of the movement.

The Third Phase of Telangana Movement Between 2009-2014

The toll inflicted upon the younger generation during the Telangana movement serves as a poignant reminder of the region's profound and enduring desire for self-governance. Between the years 2010 and 2012, a notable number of young individuals, as reported by activists, tragically ended their lives, with a subset of sixteen individuals turning to self-immolation. The sacrifice made by the individuals in question can be interpreted as an emotional appeal for increased political control and autonomy on behalf of the inhabitants of Telangana. As per the findings of the Telangana Amaraveerula Kutumbala Vedika, a platform dedicated to the families of Telangana martyrs, a significant number of 904 suicides were reported in Andhra Pradesh over the period spanning from November 2009 to February 2013. A shared demand for the establishment of the state of Telangana characterized these incidents.

The Telangana movement serves as a symbol of the Indian endeavour for both economic and cultural self-governance. The movement resembles other social and political movements originating from Osmania University. The institution facilitated the convergence of many demographic groups through its extensive educational initiatives, affording them an opportunity to express their ambitions. Osmania University emerged as the focal point of the Telangana agitation. The school served as a platform for the mobilization of demonstrations by organizations such as the Telangana Students Front (TSF) and Telangana Liberation Students Organization (TELSO), which effectively amplified the voices pushing for the autonomy of Telangana both within and outside its premises.

Formation of Telangana Joint Action Committee (TJAC/JAC)

In response to the prevailing circumstances, the Telangana Rashtra Samithi (TRS) demanded a further general strike to be held on December 24, 2009. The primary objective of this strike was to strategically impede the functioning of the regional economy, thereby garnering attention towards the pressing need to establish an independent Telangana state.

In light of the burgeoning movement, a Joint Action Committee (JAC) was established, comprising individuals affiliated with prominent political parties who endorsed the notion of an independent Telangana. Nevertheless, it is important to acknowledge that there were documented instances of substantial disparity among the Joint Action Committee (JAC) constituents about their perspectives on an independent Telangana. This observation suggests that even among proponents of separation, divergent viewpoints and approaches existed regarding the means to further their objective.

Students Joint Action Committee

Padayatras (foot marches) were planned across Telangana by students from several universities, such as Osmania, Kakatiya, Telangana, Palamuru, and Nallagonda (MG). The Student Joint Action Committee (JAC) divided into two factions, each undertaking padayatras in distinct regions, namely South and North Telangana. The series of marches reached its culmination with concluding meetings at the Kakatiya University and Osmania University, respectively. It is worth noting that the success of these padayatras was not constrained by political philosophy. The residents of Telangana, in conjunction with their elected officials at the district level, demonstrated their unwavering support, irrespective of their political alignments. The extensive commitment and solidarity within the Telangana movement are highlighted by the unity and support exhibited by several parts of society.

Undoubtedly, students have played a pivotal role in spearheading the Telangana movement. Apart from the TRSV (Telangana Rashtra Samithi Vidyarthi), various other student organizations, including ABVP, NSUI, PDSU, AISF, and Dalit Student Organization, supported the Telangana cause. On November 17, 2009, a significant event occurred at Kakatiya University, whereby a considerable assembly of student organizations met. The gathering above resulted in the establishment a Joint Action Committee (JAC) comprised of students. Subsequently, on November 23, the Joint Action Committee (JAC) was extended an invitation by K. Chandrashekar Rao, the Telangana Rashtra Samithi (TRS) leader, to support his ongoing hunger strike. This exemplifies the collective dedication to the cause.

The profound and ingrained understanding of the underlying factors among the student population originates from their early years of development. From an early age, they have been shaped by the principles of the movement. Upon the advent of the Tuition Reimbursement

Scheme (TRS) in 2001, many university students were still undergoing their secondary education. The enduring influence of TRS's objectives left a profound impression on their worldview as they matured with a deeply ingrained understanding of these principles. During instances of ambiguity or difficulty within the context of the agitation, the students have assumed a pivotal role in offering transparency and steering the movement towards the appropriate trajectory. The Telangana movement has greatly benefited from their active participation and unwavering commitment.

Students in the Telangana region have conducted several activities. During the hunger strike, these students, primarily from Osmania University, engaged in peaceful forms of protest like sit-ins, road blockades, public gatherings, and other forms of agitation within the framework of a democratic system. However, the police responded to these actions with a disproportionate use of force, injuring numerous students. The campus was secured by a police/military presence, which involved the placement of barbed wire barriers and interrupting water and power supplies to the university's hostels. In addition, they have encountered instances of termination and the use of force by law enforcement personnel on the university grounds. The government issued a proclamation granting holidays to the students and mandated their evacuation from their respective schools. In this circumstance, a student named Srikantha Chary, pursuing a degree in physiotherapy, tragically resorted to taking his own life due to the ongoing unrest. In the occurrences above, the students who tragically took their own lives expressed their support for the cause of "Jai Telangana." These incidents subsequently served as catalysts for a significant increase in student suicides, with over 600 reported cases occurring throughout various regions of Telangana.

The makeup and scope of the Telangana Movement saw a notable transformation during its second phase. This period was instigated by a group of intellectuals: professors, lawyers, employees, cultural and literary activists, and diverse caste organizations. In contrast to the previous stage, which mostly focused on urban areas, this subsequent phase transformed a widespread movement that included rural and geographically isolated regions.

Notably, the movement has exhibited exceptional durability, persisting for over twenty years during its second phase. Women have become prominent contributors to the continuing movement and have even been subjected to arrests by the state government due to their support for the establishment of a separate Telangana state. It is worth mentioning that the police have

selectively focused their attention on students hailing from Osmania and Kakatiya Universities, encompassing individuals of both genders. Osmania University continues to be a site of ongoing conflicts and law enforcement interventions. The pursuit of Telangana statehood continues unabated, displaying unwavering determination.

The Telangana movement has significantly impacted Osmania University (OU). Due to establishing a joint action committee by students residing in more than twenty-four hostels, the institution was obligated to implement the closure of its residential facilities. The aforementioned collaborative endeavour exemplifies the profound level of dedication within the student population. As a symbolic act of solidarity with Telangana, certain students have taken the initiative to modify their vehicle registration numbers, replacing the AP (Andhra Pradesh) code with TG (Telangana). This action demonstrates an individual's commitment to the cause.

The enthusiasm displayed by the students has not only reinvigorated previously inactive pro-Telangana employees' unions across several government ministries, but it has also breathed new life into the TRS, which was earlier encountering difficulties. The active involvement of students in the Telangana cause has not only revitalized the movement but has also had significant consequences for the political environment, notably for the Telangana Rashtra Samithi (TRS).

The instances above in 2009 and 2010 illustrate the confrontations and conflicts between law enforcement personnel and students affiliated with Osmania University amidst the Telangana movement. The Telangana movement witnessed the emergence of the Osmania University Joint Action Committee (OU JAC) in 2009, comprising multiple student unions affiliated with Osmania University. Nevertheless, the law enforcement authorities exhibited a severe reaction towards these demonstrations organized by the students. On February 14, 2010, an incident of severe police aggression occurred, allegedly orchestrated by Stephen Ravindra. During the incident above, the law enforcement authorities inadvertently caused damage to the lighting infrastructure within the premises of the Arts College, resulting in an unfortunate situation where the dormitory students were left without illumination. This event is one of the most intense encounters between law enforcement and student individuals.

The incident resulted in notable ramifications, as a minimum of 30 pupils incurred injuries necessitating hospitalization. Six of the individuals who sustained injuries comprised women who experienced notably serious injuries. The Human Rights Commission purportedly opposed these attacks, shedding light on police conduct in the Telangana agitation. These occurrences highlight the profound character of the movement and the difficulties encountered by the student activists in their pursuit of Telangana statehood.

On February 21, 2011, a noteworthy occurrence occurred when 16 female students from Osmania, Kakatiya, and Mahatma Gandhi Universities exhibited remarkable perseverance and drive. The individuals successfully navigated over all obstacles established by law enforcement, ultimately achieving their objective of attending the scheduled event, commonly referred to as the "Assembly Muttadi." The aforementioned courageous action exemplified the unwavering dedication of these youthful females to assert their voices and engage in the Telangana movement. The activities undertaken by individuals exemplified the enduring determination and bravery that were symbolic of the Telangana statehood struggle.

After the valiant efforts undertaken by the group of 16 girls, the ensuing occurrences were characterized by additional instances of conflict with law enforcement authorities. The individuals in question were apprehended near the Assembly. During the Million March Program, an individual named Keerthi, a student hailing from Khammam, was apprehended and subsequently detained for 14 days. Following her release, Keerthi remained actively engaged in the movement, employing her artistic abilities in singing and dancing to advance the objectives of the cause.

MLAs and ministers from Telangana have collectively tendered their resignations as a powerful demonstration of unity and dissent, urging prompt action to effectuate the division of Andhra Pradesh. Furthermore, individuals supportive of the Telangana cause and students affiliated with Osmania University engaged in a confrontation with Nagam Janardhan Reddy, a prominent Telugu Desam Party leader at the time. The individual experienced physical force, resulting in being forcefully brought down, followed by repeated strikes and kicks, until eventually finding an opportunity to flee the scene using a motorcycle. These occurrences highlight the heightened level of passion and enthusiasm exhibited by the movement during this specific timeframe.

Students in Telangana Agitation

The Telangana agitation has had a lasting impact on the region's political landscape, particularly in student activism and radicalism. The custom above, which had a surge in popularity throughout the 1970s and continued to endure subsequently, was subsequently revitalized with heightened intensity.

It is imperative to acknowledge that the genesis of the distinct Telangana movement may be attributed to a student demonstration. At its inception, the call for a distinct state was not a direct request but rather a reaction to the government's inability to effectively enforce protective measures, specifically in job and educational prospects, as stipulated in the Gentleman's Agreement established during the merger of 1956. Notably, the movement's commencement occurred without support from any political party or established politician assuming a leadership role. Indeed, officials from this particular region, including individuals affiliated with the Congress party, such as legislators and ministers, were compelled to participate in the movement after that. The statement above highlights the inherent characteristics of the Telangana movement, namely its origin at the grassroots level and its impetus led by students.

The Telangana agitation is noteworthy for being one of the most militant and protracted movements in the region's history. The protest, which students from Osmania University predominantly spearheaded, resulted in a prolonged disruption of the entire educational system, encompassing schools as well. Regrettably, the unrest led to a substantial fatality count among the student population, with an estimated 370 students perishing. Notably, the agitation also contributed to reinforcing the interpersonal connections between educators and learners. During the movement, both factions found common ground in their objectives, with notable figures such as former Vice-Chancellor Mr. Ravada Satyanarayana and then Vice-Chancellor Mr. Narotham Reddy publicly endorsing the protest. They even engaged in satyagraha, a kind of nonviolent resistance, in collaboration with the students on campus.

Despite the dedicated endeavours, the movement eventually did not attain its principal goal of forming an independent state of Telangana. The result above engendered a lasting disillusionment among the student population, who perceived themselves as being taken advantage of by politically motivated and self-interested individuals seeking to further their

partisan objectives. The sentiment above continues to persist within the student population until now.

However, the agitation had an enduring effect on the student community, rejuvenating their pride and affiliation with Osmania University. Hence, any internal or external occurrence that influenced the university's standing became closely intertwined with the broader position of the Telangana region within the state of Andhra Pradesh. The people of Telangana have attributed a newfound and noteworthy significance to several matters, including state grants allocated to the institution, admissions, academic appointments, and administrative appointments, among others. The enduring impact of the agitation continues to influence the viewpoint of the residents in the region for subsequent generations.

References:

1. Altbach, Philip, G. (July 1965), *Students Politics in Developing Countries*, American, Review, p.55.
2. Altbach, Philip, G. *India and the World Crisis*, in Altbach, RG (ed), Op.cit.,p.II.
3. Altbach, Philip, G.(1970), *A Select Bibliography on Student Politics and Higher Education*, Harvard Center for International Affairs, London, pp.24-6.
4. Anjaiah. M. (1999), *Pressure Group politics -A Study of Students' Organizations in Andhra Pradesh, Since 70s*,(Ph.D., Thesis Unpublished), Department of Political Science.
5. Di Bona, Joseph (1971), *Change and Conflict in die Indian University*, Lalvani, Bombay, p.151.
6. Lipset, S.M, and Altbach, PG (eds), (1969), *Students in Revolt*, Houghton Mifflin, Boston, p.521.
7. Mehata, Prayag (1979), *Indian Youth*, Somaiya Publication, Bombay,p.71 – 83
8. Sharma, Dev, *Campuses and Youth -in Turmoil: A perspective, in Prayang*, Mehatha, Op.cit,p79 – 80
9. Singhal, Sushila (1977), *Academic Leadership and Student-Unrest*, Newmen, New Delhi.p.157.
10. The Statesman, December 9, 1969.
11. Vishwa Yuvak Kendra (1973), *The Dyanarnic of student Agitations*, Somaiya Publications, Bombay,p.3.